

EVOLUTION AND FUNCTIONING OF FRENCH BORROWINGS IN THE
ENGLISH VOCABULARY IN THE FIELD OF FASHION

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Annotation: The topic of our thesis is “Evolution and functioning of French borrowings in the English vocabulary in the field of fashion”. Borrowings are one of the important components of vocabulary. Studying the etymology of words is a way to trace the formation of the English language, to understand which languages influenced it. In the XX-XXI centuries, the vocabulary of the English language is replenished by borrowings from other languages, in particular from French, which determines the relevance of this study.

Key words: borrowing, Gallicisms, loan words, classifications, lexical units, hybrid borrowing, word-formation.

Аннотация: Тема нашей тезис — “Эволюция и функционирование французских заимствований в английском словарном запасе в области моды”. Заимствования являются одной из важных составляющих словарного запаса. Изучение этимологии слов — это способ проследить формирование английского языка, понять, какие языки оказывали на него влияние. В XX-XXI веках словарный запас английского языка пополняется заимствованиями из других языков, в частности, из французского, что определяет актуальность данного исследования.

Ключевые слова: заимствование, галлицизмы, заимствованные слова, классификации, лексические единицы, гибридные заимствования, словообразование.

Annotatsiya: Tezisimizning mavzusi “Moda sohasidagi inglizcha lugʻatdagi fransuz tilidan oʻzlashgan soʻzlarning evolyutsiyasi va funksiyalari”. Oʻzlashma soʻzlar lugʻatning muhim tarkibiy qismlaridan biridir. Soʻzlarning etimologiyasini oʻrganish ingliz tilining shakllanishini kuzatish, unga taʼsir koʻrsatgan tillarni tushunish usulidir. XX-XXI asrlarda ingliz tilining lugʻati boshqa tillardan, xususan, fransuz tilidan oʻzlashma soʻzlar bilan boyidi, bu esa ushbu tadqiqotning dolzarbligini belgilaydi.

Kalit soʻzlar: Oʻzlashma soʻzlar, gallitsizmlar, oʻzlashma soʻzlar, tasniflash, leksik birliklar, gibrid oʻzlashmalar, soʻz hosil qilish.

The English language has a long history of borrowing from French, particularly in the fields of fashion, food, and clothing. This study explores how French borrowings have evolved and their current functioning in modern English. To analyze the integration, adaptation, and semantic evolution of French-origin words in English, focusing on their role in the cultural and social contexts of fashion, food, and clothing. The Indo-European Family is where the Germanic language that is English originated. After Chinese, it is the second most widely spoken language in the world. As of recent estimates, approximately 380 million people worldwide speak English as their first language. When including non-native speakers, the total number of English speakers rises significantly. Science, aviation, computers, diplomacy, tourism and friendship are all expressed in English. According to recent statistics, English is recognized as an official language in 67 countries and 27 non-sovereign entities; nevertheless, English is also spoken more widely and actively in other nations where it is not. [1; 222-226]

In linguistics, borrowing (also known as lexical borrowing) is the process by which a word from one language is adapted for use in another. The word that is borrowed is called a borrowing, a borrowed word, or a loanword. The English language has been described by David Crystal as an "insatiable borrower". More than 120 other languages have served as sources for the contemporary vocabulary of English. Present-day English is also a major donor language - the leading source of borrowings for many other languages. [2; 27]

The development of English lexicology is the focus of this work, which specifically examines the value of borrowed words primarily French loan words in enhancing the English language, the processes by which English vocabulary evolved and the occasions by which it acquired its extensive contemporary resources. All of these topics are of theoretical and practical interest. Furthermore, is predicated on a keen interest in the process of acquiring words from other languages, including the stages taken to give loan words their meaning, the sources from which they might be derived and the end product of this process as a way to expand and create the English vocabulary.

According to their origin, English words can be divided into two main groups: elements of one group are native words, elements of the second group are borrowed words. According to statistics, the borrowed vocabulary is much larger than the native one. According to studies, native words of the English language make up only 30% of the total number of all words.

The three hundred years of the domination of French affected English more than any other foreign influence before or after. The early French borrowings reflect accurately the spheres of Norman influence upon English life, later borrowings can be attributed to the continued cultural, economic and political contacts between the countries. The French influence added new features to the regional and social

differentiation of the language. New words, coming from French, could not be adopted simultaneously by all the speakers if English, they were first used in some varieties of the language, namely in the regional dialects of Southern England and in the speech of the upper classes, but were unknown in the other varieties of the language. [3; 56-57]

Let's analyze the "Fashion" field:

Thematic group "Fashion"

In modern etymological dictionaries there are foreign words related to this thematic group. France has always been, is and remains a trendsetter in world fashion. Therefore, it is no coincidence that French borrowings related to fashion also appeared in the English language. Let us look at some of them:

English	French	Year of borrowing	Meaning
<i>Haute couture</i>	<i>Haute couture</i>	1908	<i>haute couture – creating high-end clothing quality from leading fashion salons</i>
<i>Prêt-à-porter</i>	<i>Prêt-à-porter</i>	1959	<i>ready-made garments supplied by famous fashion designers for mass production</i>
<i>Vintage</i>	<i>Vintage</i>	1960	<i>cloth, household items, cars, etc. of the past in a modern interpretation</i>
<i>Botillions</i>	<i>Bottillions</i>	1969	<i>Low boots</i>
<i>Bustier</i>	<i>Bustier</i>	1978	<i>bustier - a piece of lingerie, a short top</i>
<i>Au courant</i>	<i>Au courant</i>	1981	<i>Fashionable, stylish</i>
<i>Faux-hawk</i>	<i>Faux-hawk</i>	2000	<i>Name hairstyles (fox hawk/hawk)</i>

A completely assimilated word is “*vintage*” (the stress has shifted to the first syllable, the word has firmly entered the English lexicon, does not seem foreign, and has an analogy with the borrowed words “*garage*”, “*mantage*”).

The word “*bustier*” belongs to the partially assimilated group (the word was assimilated phonetically and read [ˈbʌstɪər], but retained the original spelling).

Not assimilated words can be considered “*haute couture*”, “*prêt-à-porter*”, “*au courant*”, “*bottillions*” and “*faux-hawk*”. These French borrowings belong to this group because they have retained the graphic spelling, as well as features inherent in the typical French language (accent, diacritics, the continuous article “*au*” = à + le).

Some words have commonly used equivalents in English. For example, a synonym for the borrowed phrase “*haute couture*” is the English version of “high fashion”. [4; 35]

The thematic group “Fashion” contains words related to three types of assimilation: fully assimilated, partially assimilated, and not assimilated, with more of the latter than others. This is due to the fact that these words were borrowed recently. They can be found on the pages of magazines, newspapers, online blogs, as well as in advertising and catalogues. Therefore, they are for the most part not assimilated.

Language belongs to each of us. Everyone uses words. We all speak and we all listen so we are all interested in the origin of words, in how they appear and die. There is not a single language, the vocabulary of which consisted of only native words. Borrowings or loanwords play a great role in language development. All languages have borrowed some parts of its vocabulary from other languages.

The borrowing of vocabulary is rapprochement of nations on the ground of economic, political and cultural connections. The bright example of it can be numerous French borrowings to English language. For many years, borrowed words have been considered one of the important components of the vocabulary of any language. Currently, the vocabulary of the English language continues to expand thanks to various borrowings, especially French.

In conclusion, it can be noted that the results of the study provide the opportunity to use them as an applied tool in ensuring the development of dictionaries. The proposed comprehensive approach to the analysis of Gallicisms in the English language can be used for further detailed study of loanwords in other languages.

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"ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIK VA TARJIMASHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI"
mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

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